

Title: Landscape-level oilseed rape cover shapes seasonal patterns of wild bee abundance in conservation areas

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Abstract

In simplified agricultural landscapes, the continuous availability of food and nesting resources for pollinators, often associated with semi-natural habitats, is limited. This threatens pollinator populations and essential pollination services. Winter oilseed rape (OSR) can temporarily compensate for this lack of floral resources in spring by providing large amounts of nectar and pollen. While flowering OSR attracts pollinators, knowledge about its effects on pollinator populations in adjacent semi-natural habitats over the season remains vague. We therefore asked how OSR cover affects bee abundance in high-value semi-natural habitats throughout the season, and how habitat area, quality, and bee life-history traits modulate these effects. To answer this, we sampled bees in 40 semi-natural calcareous grasslands in Germany. Wild bee abundance (excluding bumblebees) in grasslands was positively related to landscape OSR cover during OSR flowering. Bumblebee abundance showed a positive relationship with OSR cover only after flowering, and only in large grasslands. Wild bees foraging on flowering OSR likely spilled over into calcareous grasslands which offer abundant nesting sites. Bumblebees, less restricted in nesting needs, built up populations in OSR-rich landscapes and benefited from continuous floral resources in large grasslands after OSR flowering. Although OSR positively affected wild bees, this effect was short-lived for non-*Bombus* bees and delayed for bumblebees. Our findings emphasize the ecological value of calcareous grasslands as high-quality foraging habitats after OSR flowering and crucial nesting sites during OSR flowering. We conclude that pollinator communities on calcareous grasslands can benefit from mass-flowering crops in the surrounding agricultural landscapes, but the conservation of these grasslands remains essential.

Keywords:

pollinators

bumblebees

mass-flowering crops

semi-natural habitats

spillover dynamics

nesting resources

habitat quality

calcareous grassland

landscape management

1. Introduction

Agricultural intensification and the loss of semi-natural habitats contribute to pollinator declines (Wagner et al., 2021), threatening essential pollination services (Garibaldi et al., 2011). A higher density of flower and nesting resources at the landscape level increases the abundance of pollinators (Mallinger et al., 2016), leading to higher crop yields (Garibaldi et al., 2013) and the conservation of insect-pollinated plants in nature conservation areas, via the pollination of wild plants (Clough et al., 2014; Klein et al., 2007; Ollerton et al., 2011). In simplified agricultural landscapes, continuous food and nesting resources for pollinators, typically provided by semi-natural habitats, are limited (Goulson et al., 2015). Mass-flowering crops, such as winter oilseed rape (*Brassica napus*, OSR), temporarily compensate for this lack of floral resources in spring by providing large amounts of nectar and pollen. Still, the effects of OSR on biodiversity are ambiguous.

Winter oilseed rape is mostly grown as energy crop for biofuel (Sieling et al., 2005). As part of the dominant winter wheat OSR rotation, it is one of the major crops in Germany with 1.08 million hectares grown in 2022 (Statistisches Bundesamt, 2024). During flowering, high cover of OSR in the landscape can lead to pollinator dilution in other crops, as its flowers are highly attractive to bees (Holzschuh et al., 2016). OSR can benefit bumblebee colony growth and increase richness and density of solitary bees in adjacent grasslands (Diekötter et al., 2014; Holzschuh et al., 2013; Riedinger et al., 2015). However, OSR may provide only limited net benefits to pollinators. Its short flowering period leads to a sudden lack of food resources after OSR flowering (Westphal et al., 2009). In addition, the promotion of a few dominant pollinator species increases competition for more specialised pollinators (Lindström et al., 2016). Finally, the frequent use of pesticides in OSR fields further harms pollinator populations (Rundlöf et al., 2015). Importantly, the effects of OSR on pollinator in ecologically high-value semi-natural habitats have not yet been thoroughly tested. This limits our understanding of how OSR affects pollinator populations that rely on semi-natural habitats for nesting or foraging beyond the mass-flowering period.

Remaining semi-natural habitats, such as calcareous grasslands, provide essential nesting and food resources for wild pollinators in intensively managed agricultural landscapes and thereby contribute to their conservation. Calcareous grasslands are heterogenous habitats with low disturbance, making them high value habitats beneficial to many pollinators (Loos et al., 2021). While these grasslands were once widespread across European landscapes, extensive grazing is no longer economically viable in many regions and many calcareous grasslands were abandoned or transformed into more profitable cropland. The remaining grasslands are now highly isolated and fragmented (Poschlod and WallisDeVries, 2002). As bees forage not only in their local habitat but also in the surrounding landscape when local food resources are scarce (Westrich, 1996), understanding the interactions

between remnant calcareous grasslands and attractive OSR is crucial for conservation. The seasonal effect of mass-flowering crops on pollinators in conservation areas like calcareous grasslands is especially understudied (Riggi et al., 2024). In addition, the area and quality of calcareous grasslands, determined by past agricultural intensification, are expected to modulate the effect of OSR cover on wild pollinators. Large calcareous grasslands usually offer more food and nesting resources than small grasslands simply because of the larger area available, leading to a reduced need for pollinators to leave the habitat and likely reducing effects of the surrounding landscape (Biegerl et al., 2025; Jauker et al., 2013). It is, however, not known whether pollinators in small, flower-poor grasslands are indeed more affected by landscape OSR cover due to limited local resources.

Including wild bee life-history traits in assessments of bee populations in conservation areas is important as wild bees are expected to respond differently to landscape OSR cover depending on their foraging range and food specialisation (Beyer et al., 2021b; Diekötter et al., 2010). This knowledge is crucial to the successful conservation of pollinators. Generalist and highly mobile bee species are expected to be more affected by landscape OSR cover than specialist, and dispersal-limited bee species, as they can forage in adjacent habitats when the local flower availability is low (Jauker et al., 2013). Conversely, small, specialist bee species are expected to depend more on local habitat factors, such as flower richness and availability, as their foraging range is small (Hopfenmüller et al., 2014; Jauker et al., 2013). These species can be expected to benefit from increasing calcareous grassland area. Among other traits such as voltinism, bee sociality may also modulate the effects of landscape OSR cover. Long-lived bumblebees and social non-*Bombus* bees are expected to be more affected by OSR as they require an increased resource continuity to feed large numbers of larvae (Becher et al., 2024). During the mass-flowering period, their colony growth benefits from the abundance of available flowers but after flowering, they must cope with a drastic reduction in food resources (Rundlöf et al., 2014). In contrast, many short-lived solitary bees have smaller nests and can complete their life cycle during short periods of resource availability. A possible effect of landscape OSR cover on these solitary bees could thus only be observed in terms of nest number and offspring in the following year (Holzschuh et al., 2013; Jauker et al., 2012), which was beyond the scope of our study.

Here, we assess the effect of landscape OSR cover during and after OSR flowering on the abundance of wild bees in 40 calcareous grasslands in two regions of northern Bavaria, Germany. Local calcareous grassland area and quality and the wild bee traits body size, sociality, food specialisation and nesting position were included in the analyses to disentangle the seasonal effects of landscape OSR cover on bee abundance in conservation areas. We aimed at answering the following questions: (i) How does an increasing cover of OSR in the landscape affect bee abundance in calcareous grasslands, a high-value habitat, during and after OSR flowering? (ii) Is the effect of landscape OSR cover on bees in calcareous

grasslands dependent of calcareous grassland area and quality? (iii) Are effects of landscape OSR cover modulated by wild bee traits?

2. Methods

2.1.

Study region and sampling sites

The study was conducted in 2022 in the surroundings of Würzburg, Lower Franconia (LF) and Bayreuth, Upper Franconia (UF), Bavaria, Germany (Figure 1). Both regions are characterised by agriculture, including intensively managed mass-flowering crops like OSR, patches of managed forests and semi-natural habitats. Calcareous grasslands, the predominant semi-natural habitat in these regions, were formerly widespread on slopes of the valleys of Franconia (Boehmer, 1994) and are nowadays embedded in an agricultural matrix and protected. The regions differ in their climatic conditions and landscape composition. The study region in Lower Franconia is characterized by higher mean annual temperatures (LF = 11.06° C, UF = 10.29° C in 2022) and a higher cover of arable land (LF = 46%, UF = 33,5%), whereas the region in Upper Franconia has a higher mean annual precipitation (LF = 566 mm, UF = 699 mm in 2022) and a higher cover of pastures (LF = 7.5%, UF = 20%) and forests (LF = 33.5%, UF = 39%).

In 2022, we selected 20 calcareous grasslands in each region as sampling sites (40 grassland sites in total) to test the effect of OSR cover in the surrounding landscape on wild bee abundance on calcareous grasslands. To cover the heterogeneity of calcareous grasslands, sampling sites were selected along gradients of calcareous grassland area (hereafter 'habitat area') (ranging from 0.07 ha to 31.54 ha). The minimum distance between sampling sites was 2 km.

Figure 1 Locations of the forty sampling sites (calcareous grasslands) in two study regions: Lower (red) and Upper Franconia (yellow) (A). Buffer of a 2 km radius around the centre of an example of a sampling site (B). Map source: © GeoBasis-DE / BKG (2023) (A) / Corine Landcover 2018 (B).

2.2.

Wild pollinators

Bees (Hymenoptera: Apiformes) were sampled using sweep-netting on the 40 sampling sites in two sampling rounds during OSR flowering (May) and after OSR flowering (June) in 2022. We analysed bumblebees separately from other wild bees, as bumblebees differ from other bees in their ecology and sociality. In the following, the term ‘wild bees’ refers to all bees except bumblebees and honeybees. We omitted honeybees altogether since honeybee abundance was low in calcareous grasslands. The order of sampling sites visited was randomized for each of the sampling rounds. We used variable transect walks with no fixed direction to sample bees. Bees were either identified visually in the field or after being caught with a sweep net and subsequently released. Transect length was 750 m and transect width was 2 m resulting in 1500 m² transect area regardless of sampling site area. Transect time was 45 minutes. Sampling was conducted from 9 am to 5 pm during suitable weather conditions (temperatures above 13° C in the sun, low wind (<3 bft), and no rain). A single person carried out collections and taxonomic identification in the field. Only wild bees and bumblebees that could not be identified to species level in the field were collected and identified in the laboratory. Bumblebee queens were not collected and were identified to species level in the field.

Wild bee species were classified as endangered (including the categories vulnerable, endangered, and critically endangered) or not endangered according to the Red List of Bavaria (Voith et al., 2021). Too few endangered bumblebee species were sampled to warrant a separate analysis of this taxon. As bees are expected to show trait based responses to OSR cover (Beyer et al., 2021b; Diekötter et al., 2010),

wild bee species were categorized in different traits according to Westrich (2019): (1) body size (bee species were split at the median of the intertegular distance (ITD); small vs large wild bees) as measure for foraging range and dispersal ability, (2) sociality (social vs solitary) as measure for nesting requirement and reproduction strategy, (3) food specialisation (polylectic vs oligolectic) as measure for gradient of specialisation and (4) nesting position (aboveground vs underground nesting) as measure for habitat and nesting requirements. We excluded bumblebee species from the trait analyses because these large and social bees would distort the results. We use bee abundance rather than species richness because a high cover of the same flower resource provided by OSR modulates the number of foraging bees and their offspring while the number of bee species depends on the diversity of flower resources (Papanikolaou et al., 2017). Because sampling effort was equal across time and area at all sampling sites, bee abundance reflects population density per transect rather than total abundance within each calcareous grassland fragment. In line with commonly used terminology and recent studies (Chase et al., 2020; Connor et al., 2000; Watling et al., 2020), we therefore refer to this measure as abundance throughout the manuscript.

2.3.

Local, landscape and OSR variables

The calculation of landscape variables was done in ArcGIS Pro 2.2.0 (Esri Inc. 2018) using aerial photos, data from the biotope mapping of Bavaria (Bayerisches Landesamt für Umwelt 2021, www.lfu.bayern.de) and the integrated management and control system for Bavarian agriculture (InVeKos, Bayerische Landesanstalt für Landwirtschaft 2022) showing detailed information about land use classes, field crops and agri-environmental schemes in 2022.

To estimate the effects of OSR cover in the surrounding landscape on bee abundance in calcareous grasslands, we calculated the percentage OSR cover within a 2 km radius of the calcareous grasslands. The landscape analysis was conducted at the 2 km scale as it can be assumed as a maximal foraging and dispersal range for most wild bees (Osborne et al., 2008; Zurbuchen et al., 2010). Additional local and landscape variables which are expected to affect bee abundance were used as control variables in the analyses (see 2.4.). These included calcareous grassland area (in ha), flower cover (estimation of the transect area covered by flowers during the transect walk; percentage) and the cover of potential nesting sites (estimation of the transect area covered by bare ground spots suitable for nesting during the transect walk; percentage) at the local scale and the mean field size of annual crop fields (measure of field margins as additional food and nesting spots in the landscape; in ha) within a 2 km radius around the centre of the sampling site at the landscape scale (Biegerl et al., 2025). OSR cover spanned a gradient from 0 to 9% and was not correlated with any other local or landscape variable in the model (Pearson correlation coefficient < 0.45; Figure S2). OSR flowered from late April until mid-May 2022 in Lower Franconia and from early May until the end of May 2022 in Upper Franconia. Therefore, sampling started in Lower Franconia in the beginning of May and in mid-May in Upper Franconia.

Figure 2 Directed acyclic graph (DAG) showing the causal structure (arrows) among local, landscape and regional variables hypothesized to be driving bee abundance. MAT = mean annual temperature (1970-2010). Explanatory variable of interest is „Oilseed rape (OSR)“. Response variable is „Bee abundance“. All other variables are control variables. The latent variable represents effects that cannot be observed or measured. The dashed lines represent unobserved relationships between local level and landscape variables.

2.4.

Statistical analysis

We designed statistical models to estimate the causal effect of OSR cover on bee abundance using structural causal modelling. To identify and account for several variables that additionally affect bees we created a directed acyclic graph (DAG) (Figure 2). DAGs help to get a clear visual representation of causal relationships, helping to identify confounders (variables that represent a common cause for an exposure and an outcome), colliders (joint effects of two variables), and the correct variables for statistical models. DAGs are built on assumptions based on expert knowledge, literature and the experience of researchers to explain the studied system and to understand complex ecological processes. More details about DAG construction, validation and possible limitations can be found in the supplementary material. We identified variables at the regional, landscape and local scale and reasonable causal relations among these variables. We applied the backdoor criterion to identify which sets of covariates were required to get an unbiased estimate of the causal effects of the explanatory variable, here landscape OSR cover (Arif and MacNeil, 2023). We validated the appropriateness of the DAG by testing DAG-data consistency, residual spatial autocorrelation and multicollinearity among variables.

The effects of landscape OSR cover on bee abundance during and after OSR flowering were estimated using generalized linear models (GLM). The response variable was bee abundance from the two respective sampling rounds (during OSR flowering and after OSR flowering), with separate models fitted for each group of wild bees (excl. bumblebees) and bumblebees. As explanatory variable, we included landscape OSR cover (continuous percentage) and as control variables / covariates, we included calcareous grassland area (log₁₀-transformed to increase linearity; continuous), flower cover during OSR flowering and after OSR flowering, respectively (continuous percentage), the area of potential nesting sites (continuous percentage), and the landscape-scale mean field size of crop fields (continuous). Adding the mean annual temperature between 1970-2010 (continuous) to the model accounts for climate driven differences in bee abundance between the two study regions that differ in climatic conditions. We tested for spatial autocorrelation using Moran's I test and found no significant patterns, indicating that the assumption of spatial independence was met. Furthermore, we tested for multicollinearity and the variance inflation factor of our predictors was always < 10, indicating no strong correlation among the predictors.

Landscape OSR cover in 2022 was positively correlated to landscape OSR cover in the preceding year (Pearson correlation coefficient: 0.64). During initial model fitting, we tested models that included landscape OSR cover of either 2022 or 2021 but as models containing landscape OSR cover of 2022

achieved better fits with lower AIC, we only included this predictor in our models (Tabel S5). Alternative models with landscape OSR cover of 2021 are shown in the supplementary material (Figure S3, Table S4).

In addition, we tested whether effects of landscape OSR cover on bees were modulated by local habitat characteristics by including interactions between OSR cover and calcareous grassland area, flower cover and the cover of potential nesting sites in the GLMs. To test trait-based responses of wild bees to landscape OSR cover, we fitted generalized linear mixed models (GLMM) including the interaction of landscape OSR cover and the bee traits (1) body size (factor, two levels: small vs large), (2) sociality (factor, two levels: social vs solitary), (3) food specialisation (factor, two levels: polylectic vs oligolectic) or (4) nesting position (factor, two levels: aboveground vs underground nesting) and a random intercept on sampling site to account for nestedness. Models were fitted using a negative binomial distribution to correct for over-dispersion in bee abundance. Model fits were visually assessed with DHARMA (Hartig and Lohse, 2022) and all models fulfilled their assumptions.

All statistical analyses were performed in R version 4.3.1 (R Development Core Team 2022). GLMMs were performed using the package *glmmTMB* (Brooks et al., 2025) and GLMs with negative binomial distribution were performed using the package *MASS* (Venables and Ripley, 2002). The package *emmeans* (Lenth et al., 2025) was used to obtain estimated marginal means for GLM(M)s. The packages *dagitty* (Textor et al., 2016), *DHARMA* (Hartig and Lohse, 2022), *car* (Fox et al., 2001), *ncf* (Bjornstand 2008) and *performance* (Lüdecke et al., 2024) were used for model validation. All graphs were generated using *ggplot2* (Wickham et al., 2024). A complete description and reproducible workflow for model fitting, validation, and visualization is provided in the supplementary material.

3. Results

We observed 192 wild bee species (33% of all species in Germany) and 4,020 wild bee individuals, of which 18 were bumblebee species (44% of all species in Germany) and 1,326 were bumblebee individuals, from May to June 2022 on 40 calcareous grasslands. According to the Red List of Bavaria 28% percent of wild bee (excluding bumblebees) and 11% of bumblebee species are endangered. During OSR flowering, we observed 118 wild bee and bumblebee species and 1,355 individuals. After OSR flowering, we observed 154 wild bee and bumblebee species and 2,665 individuals.

3.1.

Seasonal effect of OSR cover on bee abundance in calcareous grasslands

During OSR flowering, wild bee abundance in calcareous grasslands was positively related to OSR cover in the surrounding landscape, with wild bee abundance increasing by 71% for each additional 5

percentage points of OSR cover within the 2 km landscape radius and the investigated range (Figure 3A; Table S2). After flowering, wild bee abundance was not significantly affected by landscape OSR cover (Figure 3B; Table S2).

Bumblebee abundance was not significantly related to landscape OSR cover during OSR flowering (Figure 3C; Table S2). After OSR flowering, bumblebee abundance in calcareous grasslands was positively related to landscape OSR cover (Table S2). The abundance of endangered wild bees was not significantly affected by landscape OSR cover during or after flowering (Table S1, S2).

Figure 3 Relationships between bee abundance and OSR cover in 2022 for wild bees during (A) and after OSR flowering (B), bumblebees during OSR flowering (C) and after OSR flowering (D). Lines indicate relationships (estimated marginal means) between bee abundance and OSR cover. Solid lines indicate significant relationships ($p < 0.05$), dashed lines non-significant relationships ($p \geq 0.05$) and grey shaded areas represent the confidence intervals. Points represent the raw data. Regression lines were adjusted for covariates. Abundance (abun.) refers to the number of bees observed within the 1500 m² transect area.

3.2.

Differences between grasslands with low versus high local habitat quality

After OSR flowering, bumblebee abundance in large calcareous grasslands was positively related to landscape OSR cover with a 238% increase in bumblebee abundance for each 5% increase in landscape OSR cover (Figure 3D; Table S1). In small calcareous grasslands, bumblebee abundance was not significantly related to landscape OSR cover during OSR flowering (Figure 3D; Table S1). Beyond this, neither area nor quality of the calcareous grasslands modulated the effect of landscape OSR cover on bee abundance (Table S1). During and after OSR flowering, we detected no significant differences in the effect of landscape OSR cover on wild bee abundance in small, flower-poor, nesting-site-poor grasslands and large, flower-rich, nesting-site-rich grasslands.

3.3.

Influence of wild bee traits on the effect of OSR cover

During OSR flowering, the effects of landscape OSR cover on bee abundance varied between social and solitary bees. Social bee abundance was positively related to landscape OSR cover, whereas solitary bee abundance was not affected (Figure 4B; Table S3). Similarly, body size tended to modulate the effects of landscape OSR cover with small bees being marginally positively related to landscape OSR cover while large bees were unaffected (Figure 4A; Table S3). Neither nesting position nor food specialisation modulated the effects of landscape OSR cover on bee abundance (Figure 4C & D; Table S3). We found no interactions between landscape OSR cover and wild bee traits after OSR flowering (Figure S4; Table S3).

Figure 4 Relationship between wild bee abundance and OSR cover during flowering (May) separated by different life-history traits: body size (A), sociality (B), food specialisation (lecty; C) and nest position (D). Significant relationships of trait groups with OSR cover are indicated by solid lines ($p < 0.05$), not significant relationships are indicated as dashed lines ($p \geq 0.05$). Shaded areas represent the confidence intervals, points represent the raw data. Regression lines were adjusted for covariates. Abundance (abun.) refers to the number of bees observed within the 1500 m² transect area.

4. Discussion

We show that a higher cover of flowering oilseed rape (OSR) fields in the agricultural landscape led to an increasing number of wild bees (excluding bumblebees) in high-value calcareous grasslands. This result is surprising because earlier studies have shown that attractive flowering OSR fields can dilute wild bee numbers in other adjacent crop fields (Holzschuh et al., 2016; Riedinger et al., 2015; Shaw et al., 2020). For non-crop habitats, flowering OSR fields were previously reported to have no effect on wild bee populations (Riggi et al., 2024). The increased resource availability caused by the early-season flowering of OSR is generally expected to attract pollinators from other, less or similarly attractive

habitats reducing pollinator densities therein (Kovács-Hostyánszki et al., 2013; Tscharrntke et al., 2012). Despite their ecological importance, high-value habitats like calcareous grasslands have received little attention in studies assessing the impacts of mass-flowering crops on pollinators. Holzschuh et al. (2011) assessed the effect of flowering OSR cover on pollinator abundance in small calcareous grassland fragments and in OSR fields and found a weaker dilution of bees in grasslands than in OSR fields. In contrast, our findings demonstrate a positive relationship between OSR cover and the number of wild bees in high-quality habitats during OSR flowering. We assume wild bees foraging in OSR fields were attracted to the abundant nesting opportunities in calcareous grasslands and established more nests in grasslands in landscapes with higher OSR cover, rich in flower resources (Holzschuh et al., 2013). Another explanation for the positive effect during the OSR flowering is that bee populations might have built up due to the OSR food resource present in the previous year, which was positively correlated to the current year OSR cover in our analyses albeit explaining less variance when included in the models (Table S5). Therefore, we may have observed a legacy effect of past OSR flowering in the form of an enhanced bee population in the current year (Beyer et al., 2021a). Some studies reported an increased number of brood cells of cavity-nesting bees in grasslands adjacent to OSR fields, with more offspring hatching the following year (Holzschuh et al., 2013), which demonstrate that such legacy effect of OSR occur.

We did not observe any dilution of bumblebees in landscapes with high OSR cover that resulted in a decline in bumblebee abundance in calcareous grasslands during OSR flowering. This may be explained by the low abundance of bumblebees in calcareous grasslands early in the season, when only the queens were present (Holzschuh et al., 2011). In addition, bumblebees are probably not as dependent on semi-natural calcareous grassland as a nesting habitat as other wild bees, because the nesting requirements of the dominant bumblebee species are not as closely linked to calcareous grasslands as those of most other bee species (Steffan-Dewenter et al., 2002; Walther-Hellwig and Frankl, 2000). Bumblebees are likely to nest near abundant food resources and structures such as empty mouse nests that are commonly found in field margins. In contrast, most wild bee species in Central Europe are ground-nesting and depend on open soil structures such as those found in calcareous grasslands (Hopfenmüller et al., 2014; Westrich, 2019).

While we did not find effects of OSR cover on bumblebees during OSR flowering, our study is the first to demonstrate a positive and time-delayed effect of high OSR cover on bumblebees in large, high-value calcareous grasslands after OSR flowering. The resource pulse during OSR flowering likely promoted the early growth of bumblebee colonies in habitats adjacent to OSR fields, which could also include calcareous grasslands (Herrmann et al., 2007; Westphal et al., 2003). However, it is important for social bees to have a high continuity of resources, so bumblebees must cope with a sudden lack of

food after OSR flowering (Rundlöf et al., 2014). Therefore, once the OSR had finished flowering, bumblebees foraged in the surrounding landscape (Kovács-Hostyánszki et al., 2013) and were then attracted to habitats abundant and rich in flowers, which were, among other places, found in large calcareous grasslands. To conclude, we probably observed stronger bumblebee colony growth in landscapes with a high OSR cover and thus a higher spillover of bumblebees to calcareous grasslands or a higher number of bumblebee individuals, because of established colonies in calcareous grasslands surrounded by higher OSR cover.

In contrast to bumblebees, the initial pulse of OSR flowers did not increase wild bee abundances in calcareous grasslands once the flowers had finished blooming. The few other studies that have assessed pollinator abundance after OSR flowering did also not detect spillover from mass-flowering crops to non-crop habitats for wild bees (Hanley et al., 2011; Montero-Castaño et al., 2016; Riggi et al., 2024). We assume that (1) bees that use OSR as food resource profit from high nectar and pollen resources but are simultaneously negatively affected by a rather one-sided and unfavourable food supply, as has been shown for other pollen types (Di Pasquale et al., 2013). However, these opposing effects primarily concern social bee species, which have a longer reproductive period during the season and produce a higher number of offspring per nest compared to solitary bees. To meet the nutritional demands of their numerous larvae, social bees prefer to nest in landscapes with high OSR cover. Yet, the poor nutritional quality of OSR pollen negatively affects their reproductive success. As a result, the benefits of abundant floral resources may be offset by the drawbacks of poor food quality after OSR flowering (Jauker et al., 2012). (2) The positive effect of OSR on wild bees other than bumblebees during flowering is offset by the increasing number of bumblebees in June, resulting in resource competition and / or (3) wild bees benefitting from OSR during flowering may have already finished their adult phase prior to our assessment after OSR flowering. In contrast, generalist bumblebees benefit from flowering OSR for early colony growth and later depend on the resource continuity of calcareous grasslands. Previous studies, however, found that the positive effects of OSR on bumblebee colonies did not result in a higher production of sexuals and therefore not necessarily to higher abundance in the following year (Hovestadt et al., 2019; Westphal et al., 2009). Positive effects of OSR on bumblebees should therefore be viewed with caution.

Area and quality of the calcareous grasslands did not modulate the effect of landscape OSR cover on bee abundance, except for bumblebees after OSR flowering. The temporal spillover and the higher abundance of bumblebees on calcareous grasslands, probably driven by stronger colony growth in landscapes with high OSR cover, was only observed in large calcareous grasslands, where food resources are more consistently available (Biegerl et al., 2025). Large colonies of social bumblebees, in particular, depend on a constant, plentiful supply of food (Rundlöf et al., 2014) and increasingly use

these large, resource-rich grasslands after OSR flowering to provide for their offspring. In landscapes with low OSR cover bumblebee abundance was low on small and large grasslands. In contrast, wild bees in large and small calcareous grasslands were supported by a higher landscape OSR cover during OSR flowering. Instead of an expected dilution of wild bees in small, flower- and nesting-site-poor habitats during OSR flowering because of limited resources, we observed a concentration, presumably as wild bees were attracted to nesting sites in calcareous grasslands irrespective of their area and quality. Our results suggest that all studied calcareous grasslands provide sufficient food and nesting resources to be highly attractive to nest-searching wild bees during OSR flowering.

When we considered the life-history traits of wild bees, we found that the positive relation between landscape OSR cover and wild bee abundance in calcareous grasslands was driven by social and small bees. Social and small species (e.g. *Halictus tumulorum*, *Lasioglossum interruptum*) are more likely than solitary bees to exploit only one or a few floral resources in landscapes with high OSR cover, specifically the available flowers of mass-flowering crops (Smith et al., 2019). Social bees need to feed more offspring and therefore prefer to use the abundant flowers. Consequently, there are many social bees in the OSR fields and the surrounding area; and these bee species are thus more likely to find suitable nesting habitats in adjacent calcareous grasslands. This spatial association leads to increased abundances of social bees in these habitats, as colonies focus extensively on brood production during the OSR flowering period. In particular, the first brood predominantly consists of worker bees, which contribute to colony growth by intensive foraging, which can further increase the presence of social bees in calcareous grasslands (Hovestadt et al., 2019). Solitary bees, such as *Andrena flavipes* and *Osmia bicolor*, which also forage on OSR and were abundant in our calcareous grasslands during the flowering period, did not increase in number as the cover of OSR increased. Unlike social bees, solitary bees do not produce worker bees and positive effects of OSR cover would thus only be seen in a higher number of nests or offspring in the following year, at least for univoltine species (Holzschuh et al., 2016; Jauker et al., 2012). Furthermore, in our study solitary bees generally had a larger body size than social non-*Bombus* bees resulting in a higher mobility. Solitary bees can therefore search for food, and consequently nesting sites, over a wider area of the surrounding landscape and thus also find alternatives to OSR (Bänsch et al., 2021). They may also compete with social bees for nesting sites around OSR fields, which are often occupied by large groups of social bees. This might force solitary bees to look for alternative nesting sites.

Conclusion

As oilseed rape (OSR) is the most common mass-flowering crop in Germany, understanding its temporal effects on pollinators in high-value habitats is crucial for future conservation approaches. Our study emphasizes the importance of considering landscape-level factors when evaluating the conservation

of wild pollinators in such habitats. We demonstrate that landscape OSR cover affects abundances of bees, even in high-value habitats, such as calcareous grasslands. However, the positive effect of OSR cover is very short-lived for non-*Bombus* bees and only detectable for bumblebees after OSR flowering. Given the limited temporal availability of this resource, it seems unlikely that the production of queens in bumblebees foraging on OSR and inhabiting calcareous grasslands will increase with increasing landscape OSR cover (Westphal et al., 2009).

Our findings emphasize the ecological value of calcareous grasslands not only as high-quality flower resources after OSR flowering, but also as crucial nesting habitats during the mass-flowering period (Gardein et al., 2022; Hopfenmüller et al., 2014). Remarkably, their value persists irrespective of area or quality of the grassland fragments. We conclude that pollinator communities on calcareous grasslands can benefit from mass-flowering crops in the surrounding agricultural landscapes, but the conservation of these grasslands remains essential. In addition, our study highlights the importance of identifying the key factors that drive observed ecological patterns in mass-flowering crop studies with ambiguous outcomes. Variables like landscape cover of the mass-flowering crop, habitat area of focal patches, pollinator traits, and temporal resource dynamics may all play critical roles and interact. More broadly, our findings emphasize the necessity of considering the temporal context and population dynamics in ecological studies, not only for wild bees and calcareous grasslands, but also across other taxa and habitat types.

Ethics. Permission to enter nature conservation areas and to collect wild pollinators was granted by the nature conservation authorities of Lower Franconia (permit number RUF-55.1.2-8646.7-4-42-8 issued by government of Lower Franconia) and Upper Franconia (permit number 55.1-8622 issued by the government of Upper Franconia).

Data availability. All datasets and the R code supporting this article will be made publicly available at the Zenodo library upon acceptance.

Declaration of AI use. We have not used AI-assisted technologies in creating this article.

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Authors' contributions. C.B.: formal analysis, investigation, methodology, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; A.H.: conceptualization, methodology, writing—review and editing; F.B.:

formal analysis, writing—review and editing; J.K.: conceptualization, methodology, writing—review and editing; J.Z.: data curation, writing—review and editing; I.S.D.: conceptualization, methodology, writing—review and editing, funding.

All authors contributed significantly to revisions and gave final approval for publication.

Conflict of interest declaration. We declare we have no competing interests.

Figure legends

Figure 1 Locations of the forty sampling sites (calcareous grasslands) in two study regions: Lower (red) and Upper Franconia (yellow) (A). Buffer of a 2 km radius around the centre of an example of a sampling site (B). Map source: © GeoBasis-DE / BKG (2023) (A) / Corine Landcover 2018 (B).

Figure 2 Directed acyclic graph (DAG) showing the causal structure (arrows) among local, landscape and regional variables hypothesized to be driving bee abundance. MAT = mean annual temperature (1970-2010). Explanatory variable of interest is „Oilseed rape (OSR)“. Response variable is “Bee abundance”. All other variables are control variables. The latent variable represents effects that cannot be observed or measured. The dashed lines represent unobserved relationships between local level and landscape variables

Figure 3 Relationships between bee abundance and OSR cover in 2022 for wild bees during (A) and after OSR flowering (B), bumblebees during OSR flowering (C) and after OSR flowering (D). Lines indicate relationships (estimated marginal means) between bee abundance and OSR cover. Solid lines indicate significant relationships ($p < 0.05$), dashed lines non-significant relationships ($p \geq 0.05$) and grey shaded areas represent the confidence intervals. Points represent the raw data. Regression lines were adjusted for covariates. Abundance (abun.) refers to the number of bees observed within the 1500 m² transect area.

Figure 4 Relationship between wild bee abundance and OSR cover during flowering (May) separated by different life-history traits: body size (A), sociality (B), food specialisation (lecty; C) and nest position (D). Significant relationships of trait groups with OSR cover are indicated by solid lines ($p < 0.05$), not significant relationships are indicated as dashed lines ($p \geq 0.05$). Shaded areas represent the confidence intervals, points represent the raw data. Regression lines were adjusted for covariates. Abundance (abun.) refers to the number of bees observed within the 1500 m² transect area.

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